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Human resources management: A perspective for the company ESPO S.A.

Jesús David Velásquez – Ascanio *

Faculty of Administrative and Economic Sciences, Francisco de Paula Santander University, Ocaña, Colombia.

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Abstract

The management of human talent is essential for the sustainability of companies, nowadays globalization has increased the exchange of cultures and has evolved the social behavior of people. This article presents the concept of strategic planning and human talent management for Empresa de Servicios Públicos de Ocaña S.A., hereinafter ESPO S.A., in order to determine the importance of human resources within companies. A survey elaborated by Dr. Cesar Nieto will be applied in order to evaluate and analyze the results related to the human management of ESPO S.A.

Finally, strategic planning policies are proposed in accordance with the company's business model and a human talent management proposal is presented to contribute to the fulfillment of the strategic plan.

Keywords: Human talent management; Strategic planning; Human resources; Sustainability; Balanced scorecard

1. Introduction

ESPO S.A. as a public utilities company of private character and regulated by Law 142 of 1994, develops its strategic plan in the search to meet the demands of the community and the current regulations, for this reason the fulfillment of its legal and social mission is related to the improvement of the quality of life of the inhabitants of the city of Ocaña, through a timely, correct and continuous provision of public utilities of water, sewerage and sanitation.

The company's mission is focused on working with a spirit of social responsibility, effectiveness, sustainability and sustainability in the provision of public services, meeting the needs of drinking water and basic sanitation under the standards of quality and continuity, improving the quality of life of the people of Ocaña. The company expects to lead in 2030 in Ocaña and the province the operation of public utilities offered under the standards of sustainability, competitiveness and respect for the ecosystem. [1].

The strategic plan of ESPO S.A. aims at social responsibility and environmental sustainability, this plan agrees with what was stated by [2] in their research, in which they determined that the vast majority of companies in the city of Ocaña are becoming accustomed to implement internal and external practices of social and environmental responsibility, generating a commitment to the community that contributes to the solution of social problems and encouraging the good use of non-renewable resources (p.6).

[3] Stated that worldwide economic growth has affected the environment through the indiscriminate use of its resources. However, various organizations, student movements, entrepreneurs and society in general have become aware of the importance of proposing strategies aimed at the sustainable strengthening of current organizations and new business ideas, in which not only the economic factor prevails, but also environmental and social aspects are included.

* Corresponding author: Jesús David Velásquez – Ascanio

Faculty of Administrative and Economic Sciences, Francisco de Paula Santander University, Ocaña, Colombia.

The current situation of the company requires a change in its organizational policies, taking into account the competition currently generated by the globalization of markets and the needs of stakeholders. In order to achieve a competitive advantage and implement actions to achieve it, it is initially proposed to organize the company horizontally seeking to assign responsible for the mission processes of ESPO S.A. fulfilling the value proposition to customers.

2. Theoretical Framework

[4] In his book mentions the four perspectives that the balanced scorecard of an organization should contain: Internal, financial, customers and training and growth. The scorecard of the company ESPO S.A. complies with the four perspectives described by Fernandez, which seek as a final result to ensure the continuous and efficient provision of services, through a synergy of each of them. Strengthening the human management cycle, designing the environmental management system, improving the operation of the water, sewage and sanitation systems, optimizing the commercial service processes, consolidating the institutional positioning, optimizing costs and expenses, maximizing income, expanding new businesses, improving the quality and continuity of service provision and consolidating environmental projects; these are the components of the four perspectives of the scorecard described by Fernandez in his book for the company.

Each perspective of the balanced scorecard is fundamental for the sustainability of an organization, but more than that, it must have a valuable partner to execute this strategy, i.e. a leader behind each process. It should be emphasized that leadership consists of the ability to influence a group of followers through the union of individual wills and organizational values, allowing through creativity, respect and a vision of the future to work towards common objectives that satisfy general needs [5].

For the execution of policies and compliance with organizational management, it is important that the company implements strategies that facilitate innovation, increase efficiency and productivity, streamline processes, satisfy internal and external users, focus and promote human talent and finally generate value for shareholders.

When implementing organizational management policies, it is important to take into account the available budget and the impact that the lack or depletion of this item may have on the human management strategy. [6] In their research concluded that one of the causes that generate financial losses in an organization is the poor management of human resources and consequently a bad working environment that results in unproductivity, therefore, they recommended defining a very good salary policy and strategies that encourage an appropriate organizational climate and culture.

3. Methodology

To determine the valuation of human management in the company ESPO S.A., an information gathering instrument elaborated by Dr. Cesar Nieto for his doctoral thesis will be applied. The measurement instrument comprises a structure that classifies the eighty-two questions related to the human talent management process in three dimensions, named as: purposes, processes and competencies, then the score for each of them is determined on a scale of 0 to 4 and thus be able to propose according to the result obtained the improvement strategies [7].

It is worth mentioning that the company in question does not have a human resources area; therefore, the impact assessment survey was conducted by the company's legal department, which is currently in charge, among other legal aspects, of hiring personnel. In order to facilitate the analysis of the survey results, a rating scale was proposed: Strength from 75 to 100 points, to be improved from 50 to 74.9 points, low from 25 to 49.9 points and weak below 25 points.

4. Results

The results by purpose dimension yielded a value of 22.63, processes 15.7 and competencies 19.5, generally reflecting a weak human resources management within the company. The results are a consequence of the lack of a specific human resources area to manage talent and execute the respective strategies, even more so when the legal area only takes care of the legal aspects of hiring personnel, but does not guarantee their development.

The lack of a human management competency model (score 0.0) is reflected in the way personnel are selected and subsequently trained to start working, in addition to not measuring the performance of employees, resulting in problems in establishing salary increases or economic incentives within the company.

These results reflect the little development that human management has had within the company, despite having an occupational health and safety program, facilitating staff training and a bonus program established in Law 142 of 1994. A person in charge of the area who inspires confidence is not enough to become a business strategy as stated by [8] who explains that human management should support the fulfillment of the company's strategic plan, which should implement human talent policies according to the company's own reality, through a reflective, analytical and contextualized process.

The results of ESPO S.A. obtained in the application of Dr. Nieto's instrument are the consequence of the lack of a human talent management area and leader. These results agree with the research carried out by [9] in which they determined that a recurrent problem in the real estate company under study is the difficulty to perform a dynamic work, because due to the excessive workload and the lack of role assignment, a physical and emotional wear and tear was caused to the related personnel.

5. Discussion and proposal

A society was considered strong according to the amount of resources it had both in capital and land, today, knowledge is the source of power in the organizations of the XXI century, therefore, organizational learning is of great importance as a generator of value and as a mediator in increasing productivity and sustainability. This learning model must be adjusted to the needs and realities of the companies, anchored to the human talent management process [10].

Taking into account the current situation of ESPO S.A. due to the lack of a human management area and in view of the importance and the differential factor that human talent and knowledge can have compared to other companies in the sector in terms of competitiveness, it is proposed to the company the creation of the human resources area, led by a professional with technical experience in the area and with soft skills such as teamwork, trust, resilience, respect, among others.

The proposal includes the elaboration of a strategic planning of the human resources area in order to align it with the strategic plan of ESPO S.A. and in this way help to fulfil the policies initially proposed. It is important that the company reviews and restructures the design of the positions and the profile of the needs of the respective position, for which it is proposed to redesign the manual of functions that ESPO S.A. currently has and based on this to elaborate a recruitment and selection policy that includes a psycho-technical test and finally a personnel training program.

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Professor [11] built a model of human management for SMEs, determining that people are the most valuable central axis for companies, coinciding with the need for innovation and resilience that companies must have in the face of constant social, economic and cultural changes that humanity has had, therefore human talent will be essential for business sustainability, this is possible if the staff is motivated, trained and committed; concluding the importance of the development of human management within the company. For which I propose a model of human management, starting with the strategic direction that includes the administrative processes of human management such as recruitment, selection, training and evaluation, as well as everything necessary to ensure personal and professional development within the company in the pursuit of personal welfare aligned with the objectives of the company.

Additionally, [12] considers that in order to achieve an adequate strategic planning of the human resources area, which is what the company under study needs, a series of steps must be followed. Starting with the construction of the mission, vision and values of the area, followed by an analysis of the internal environment, formulation and implementation of the strategy and finally the assessment and evaluation of human resources management.

Finally, [13] proposes five macro processes that companies should follow for an adequate implementation of the human talent management staff: 1) strategic planning of the human management area, 2) recruitment, selection and induction of people to the organization, 3) salary scale, safety and hygiene of people, 4) growth and training of personnel and 5) emotional ties with the employee. By complying with these macro-processes in a sequential manner, the author states that the company will obtain an adequate human talent management.

6. Conclusion

A proposal for the implementation of the human resources area for ESPO S.A. was determined with the objective of aligning the human talent management strategies with the company's strategic plan, considering the weaknesses found with the application of the measurement instrument and the current trends aimed at the retention, development and welfare of people.

With the human talent management proposal, it is expected that the human resources area will generate improvement strategies, guaranteeing from the beginning of the personnel selection stage those who have the best competencies that will help ESPO S.A. to comply with its strategic planning.

The impact will be measured through a 360° performance evaluation, which will reveal the needs presented by the personnel, as well as the organizational climate of the company. Based on the results, improvement strategies will be established.

Finally, the proposed objectives are met by suggesting to the company a series of policies and proposals that will facilitate the fulfillment of the business model, allowing the company to sustain itself in the financial, social and organizational aspects.

Compliance with ethical standards

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To the employees of the company ESPO S.A.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author has no conflict of interest to declare. The author has seen and agrees with the content of the manuscript.

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Author's short Biography

Public Accountant Master of Business Administration -MBA and specialist in tax planning, trained and experienced in the public and private sectors leading the accounting and tax processes in organizations, preparation of financial reports with IFRS policies, preparation of financial projections and budget planning and control. Full-time professor of the business administration program.